

Pinpointing the Sun's Neighbors Within Vast Data Archives

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Mapping the solar neighborhood is a time-honored quest in the field of astronomy, but surprisingly many of our closest substellar neighbors have gone overlooked. By fully scouring vast archives hosting modern survey datasets, we can uncover more of the faintest and coldest nearby brown dwarfs, thereby gaining critical insights about the substellar mass function and exoplanet atmospheres. Our [Backyard Worlds](#) citizen-science project is searching for cold and close substellar objects by combining the power of data archives with a legion of over 100,000 dedicated volunteers. The Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI) Legacy Imaging Surveys provide the main datasets that Backyard Worlds citizen-scientists explore: custom infrared sky maps from NASA's *WISE* satellite [1] and wide-area red-optical imaging [2], [3] from the Dark Energy Survey (DES), Dark Energy Camera Legacy Survey (DECaLS), and Mayall z-band Legacy Survey (MzLS). Backyard Worlds volunteers scrutinize these datasets for objects that are both unusually red and fast-moving, the telltale indicators of cold and nearby brown dwarfs (Figure 1).

Billion-object catalogs are far too large for each Backyard Worlds participant to simply download their own copy. Thankfully, the Community Science and Data Center's [Astro](#)

Figure 1. These screengrabs of the [DESI Legacy Surveys sky viewer](#) show how its combination of data from WISE/Blanco/Mayall can aid in the process of brown dwarf discovery and vetting. The arrows point to the brown dwarf, which looks orange in WISE and deep red in DESI Legacy Surveys data from Blanco/Dark Energy Camera (DECam). (Credit: CTIO/MSO/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/DOE)

[Data Lab](#) hosts these large modern datasets, enabling Backyard Worlds citizen-scientists to conveniently issue queries for new brown dwarf candidates. Discoveries made in this

way by members of the general public underscore Astro Data Lab's excellent combination of accessibility, open data practices, and advanced science platform functionality.

We recently completed a *Spitzer Space Telescope* follow-up campaign targeting ~ 100 of the coolest Backyard Worlds discoveries [4]. *Spitzer* provides the crucial brown dwarf temperature estimates, separating out the coldest Y dwarfs ($T_{\text{eff}} < 500$ K) from more numerous and warmer T dwarfs. Several of our new Backyard Worlds discoveries are among the coldest brown dwarfs yet known. These objects begin bridging a previously wide gap between the coolest known brown dwarf and the broader substellar population (Figure 2). These results demonstrate the ability of citizen-scientists to reshape our understanding of the Sun’s cosmic neighborhood.

Looking to the future, Backyard Worlds is preparing to publish follow-up observations of even more brown dwarf discoveries, obtained with telescopes including NOIRLab’s Gemini North, Gemini South, SOAR, and Blanco. Thanks to initiatives such as the Rubin Observatory Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST), archival mining of large survey datasets—through methodologies including citizen science and machine learning—is poised to play a central role in the coming decades of astronomical research.

References

- [1] Meisner, A. M., Lang, D., & Schlegel, D. J. 2018, *AJ*, 156, 69
- [2] Abbott, T. M. C., et al. 2018, *ApJS*, 239, 18
- [3] Dey, A., et al. 2019, *AJ*, 157, 168
- [4] Meisner, A. M., et al. 2020, *ApJ*, 899, 123

Figure 2. The red data points discovered by Backyard Worlds participants help fill in a wide gap between the bulk of the previously known Y dwarf population (gray and black data points) and WISE 0855–0714, the coldest known brown dwarf. WISE 0830+2837, discovered by citizen-scientist Dan Caselden, stands out as a potential “missing link” in the Y dwarf population. (From [4], with permission)